

Efficient Canonical Encoding of Plane Trees as Proper Fractions

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Abstract

An efficient injective mapping from the **plane trees (PTs)** into **proper fractions** in the interval $[0, \frac{2}{3})$ is introduced. The encoding—which concomitantly establishes a total ordering—is generated in linear time and is **invertible by inspection**. The work departs from prior art by reexamining the problem through the interdisciplinary lenses of syntactic pattern recognition and formal language theory, deriving a strict specification of PT structure from a compact picture description language (PDL) governed by a context-free grammar (CFG).

KEYWORDS: plane trees, ordered trees, structural encoding, tree encoding, prime tree encoding, bijection, ternary encoding, rational numbers, picture description language, context-free grammar.

1 Picture description language

It should be straightforward to encode plane trees (PTs). The identification of a unific paradigm for this fundamental problem in syntactic pattern recognition has proven strangely elusive. Perhaps the confusion would be alleviated by the introduction of a **picture description language**, or PDL [5, pp. 36ff.], consisting of three PT-building **primitives**:

- 1 = **descent** (\swarrow) to leftmost child;
- 2 = **rightward motion** (\rightarrow) to next sibling; and
- 0 = **ascent** (\nwarrow) to parent.

This “language” enables **any PT to be described by some string**, $R \in LL^*$, that charts a depth-first traversal, where LL^* is the positive Kleene closure of L . We initially require that the

traversal explicitly return to the root from the rightmost leaf as a structural integrity check. Figure 1 demonstrates the encoding of a decidedly nontrivial (*viz.*, 20 nodes, depth 4) sample PT.

Figure 1. This PT is described by the string **11212 10022 02112 20021 21102 000**.
(White space is interspersed to facilitate reading and verification.)

Conceptually, we have captured **instructions for drawing the PT**:

↙, ↙, →, ↙, →, ↙, ↖, ↖, →, →, ↖, →, ↙, ↙, →,
→, ↖, ↖, →, ↙, →, ↙, ↙, ↖, →, ↖, ↖, ↖

using the alphabet $L = \{0, 1, 2\}$ because it is easier to work with than $L_0 = \{\nwarrow, \swarrow, \rightarrow\}$. The encoding can be interpreted as a **ternary** (base-three) **proper fraction** with radix point to the left of the highest-order digit. In the case of the PT shown in Figure 1, the **string** $R \in LL^*$, which constitutes its **Wilner encoding**:

11212 10022 02112 20021 21102 000

immediately maps to the **nonnegative rational**:

0.11212 10022 02112 20021 21102₃. □

Proceeding more formally, we first map ASCII numerals to the corresponding numbers via the function $\Lambda : L = \{\lambda_i\} \mapsto Z_{\geq 0} = \{\zeta_i\}$, defined as $\Lambda(\lambda_i) = \zeta_i \mid i \leq 3$, whereby the string $R = \{r_i\} \in LL^*$ yields the rational number:

$$WE = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{|R|} 3^{|R|-i} \Lambda(r_i) \right) / 3^{|R|}.$$

Mere **inspection** of the Wilner encoding, $\llbracket WE \rrbracket$ —*a fortiori*, of its numerator alone—inverts the mapping, since the **ternary digit sequence offers complete instructions for rebuilding the PT**. The WE always terminates with a run of zeroes that describes the stepwise ascent from the rightmost leaf back to the root. **The WE of the degenerate lone root is arbitrarily chosen as 0**. Note that the Wilner encoding:

(i) never evinces **leading zeroes**—other than in the degenerate case—while the choice of $0 \in L$ to represent the ascent primitive makes any **trailing zeroes**, our “structural integrity check,” as **numerically** superfluous as they are **descriptively** redundant; moreover, is:

(ii) **isomorphic**—except for the uninformative trailing zeroes—whether interpreted as

(a) a string of characters or

(b) a fixed-point ternary significand with radix point leftmost;

(iii) **injective onto the discontinuous rational number interval**, $\{0\} \cup \left[\frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}\right)$: the infimum of the interval, 0, encodes the degenerate PT, while its nearest neighbors— 0.1_3 , 0.11_3 , 0.111_3 , *etc.*—encode successive n -node PTs of depth $n - 1$, where $n \geq 2$; the supremum of the interval, $0.\overline{1222}_3$, encodes the depth-one PT with \aleph_0 leaf children; and **No fraction can begin with 0.2₃**, as the depth-first traversal of a PT cannot move rightward (2) without first descending (1);

(iv) **irreducible**, as its numerator ends in either 1_3 or 2_3 —unless zero-valued—while its denominator is a power of three;

(v) **bijective onto the PTs**: every PT corresponds to a unique Wilner encoding and vice versa—assuming that the encoding is **legal**, as addressd in Section 2;

(vi) **readily invertible**, as any PT can immediately be reconstructed from its Wilner encoding;

(vii) **computable in linear time**, $O(n)$, as the traversal of a PT with node count $n \geq 2$ visits every leaf once and every internal node twice;

(viii) **extremely compact**, since (v) implies that encoding an n -node tree requires $< 2n$ ternary digits—*e.g.*, the 19-node PT of Figure 1 required 26 digits—which can be accommodated by only $\left\lceil 2n \frac{\ln 3}{\ln 2} \right\rceil \approx \lceil 3.17n \rceil$ bits; and

(ix) **order-establishing**: for any two PTs, u and v , $WE(u) \neq WE(v)$, which, with (ii), is sufficient to establish a total order over the countably infinitely numerous PTs; moreover, the ordering is **intuitive**, as:

- (a) $WE(u) < WE(v)$ implies that u is **deeper toward the left** or **narrower toward the root** than v : in particular,
- (b) deletion of the rightmost leaf from u yields a new PT, u' , that always obeys $WE(u') < WE(u)$. This follows because dropping a nonzero terminal digit from the numerator reduces the fraction by discarding nonzero information. \square

2 Context-free grammar

The trailing zeroes that we freely truncate from both the string and numeric representations of the Wilner encoding are **not** altogether superfluous: they offer an expedient check on the consistency of a specification. In particular—excepting the degenerate case—every valid specification in R must be **balanced**, supplying a 0 to “undo” each 1 incurred while traversing the tree. Ergo, if there is any deficit of 0s, then we have not reached the end of the specification.

It is impossible to characterize these mandatory semantics using, *e.g.*, the regular expression notation [1, pp. 94ff.]. It is certainly true that, other than in the case of the degenerate lone root (encoded as 0), the Wilner encoding of a PT matches the regular expression $1[012]^*0$ —representing initial descent below the root (**1**) and eventual reascent thereto (**0**), perhaps with arbitrary activity ($[012]^*$). The converse is untrue. For example, the string 120210 matches the regular expression and, *a fortiori*, is balanced, but it does not correctly describe a constructible PT. We are therefore justified in imposing a **formal grammar** atop the strings $R \in LL^*$ so that only those strings that correspond to constructible PTs are legal.

To clarify how such a grammar might be organized, let us first more concretely specify a traversal of a nondegenerate PT that constructs its string specification, $R \in LL^*$, in parallel:

```

traverse PT:
  append a '1' to R
  if  $\exists$  a leftmost non-leaf child, L:
    traverse L
  for each child, C, rightward of L {
    append a '2' to R
    if C is a non-leaf:
      traverse C
  }
  append a '0' to R

```

This procedure can only generate strings of a certain narrowly defined structure. These strings can be characterized by a **context-free grammar** [1, pp. 165ff.] expressed in Backus-Naur Form, or BNF [9, pp. 146ff.]. The grammar derives a sentence from the start symbol $\langle R \rangle$. Semantic interpretation of the nonterminal, $\llbracket \langle R \rangle \rrbracket$, is required to obtain the string R , a well-formed Wilner encoding. This is because BNF can only describe input structures: it is our **interpretation** that builds the associated ternary digit strings.

```

<R>      ::=  0
           |  <S>
<S>      ::=  1 <leftmost> 0
           |  1 <leftmost> <siblings> 0
<siblings> ::=  2 <leftmost>
           |  <siblings> 2 <leftmost>
<leftmost> ::=  ε
           |  <S>

```

Fans of notoriously non-standardized Extended Backus-Naur Form (EBNF) [7, pp. 110ff.] may prefer the less prolix alternative:

```

R          = "0" | S;
S          = "1" leftmost { "2" leftmost } "0";
leftmost  = [ S ];

```

which cannot be further simplified, as it is illegal to define a nonterminal recursively.

For those unacquainted with context-free grammars, the BNF rules specify a **lookahead parser**, a finite state machine that can **recognize** the grammar by transitioning among states corresponding to partially assembled grammatical structures [1, pp. 215ff.]. Lookup tables specify which input **tokens** encountered in which state cause the machine to transition to which respective successor states. The tokens in this case are not strings in LL^* , but consecutive individual characters thereof. A well-formed input sequence will be fully consumed and drive the automaton to its terminal “complete sentence recognized” state. Tools have been available since the 1970s to automatically generate a C or FORTRAN parser for a given BNF grammar.

3 Comparison of the Wilner encoding to competitive schemes

There have been numerous attempts to establish a universal encoding scheme for trees, but nothing seems to have quite caught on. I endeavor *infra* to present a balanced survey of prior art that contrasts relative strengths and weaknesses. The analysis distills what **I regard** as the essences of the competing schemes, so I apologize for any inadvertent misrepresentations.

Dyck words are arguably the foundational representational construct for PTs. They use nested () pairs to specify parent-child relationships and support nodes of arbitrary order, with siblings juxtaposed in sequence. Dyck words are structurally identical to degenerate LISP s-expressions, albeit the storage structure that underlies the homologous “sibling” construct in LISP is rather more byzantine, since the language only natively supports **binary** trees. Dyck words are commonly converted to bit strings by mapping ‘(’ to 1 and ‘)’ to 0; Kása, *e.g.*, demonstrates the total ordering of such bit strings over the four-node binary trees but cannot generally extend the scheme to all PTs [8, pp. 114ff.]. Putatively superior representations like LOUDS and DFUDS are merely variations on Dyck words that may optimize certain classes of algorithms but do not ultimately increase either expressiveness or conciseness [6].

A Prüfer sequence can also represent an arbitrary PT. However, this requires the imposition of an explicit node labeling scheme—or, at the very least, the enforcement of a strict “dismantle rightmost, reconstruct leftmost” protocol. Variations on the Prüfer sequence have been devised to, *e.g.*, optimize the encoding of phylogenetic binary trees [10]. The essential problem with encodings of this class is their brute-force, procedural approach, which yields lengthy sequences of seemingly random integers with no discernible pattern, let alone total ordering.

Yet other encoding strategies seem to have been force-fitted atop paradigms that were chosen solely because they support clean separation and recombination, *e.g.*, proper fractions, continued fraction expansions, products of powers of primes. (Calkin and Wilf’s convenient bijection of binary tree **nodes** to proper fractions [3] is not addressed because it does not readily extend to PT **structures**.) Tropashko has demonstrated [11] the use of continued fractions to encode the **path from the root to a node**, $3 + \frac{1}{7 + \frac{1}{4 + \frac{1}{6}}}$ encoding the path {3,7,4,6}, *e.g.* Unfortunately, to

characterize an entire PT in this fashion would require a unique continued fraction for every leaf, and there is no expedient means for aggregating and subsequently recovering the individual fractions. Moreover, decoding paths from such fractions requires repeated evaluation of reciprocals, incurring cumulative truncation and rounding errors that eventually lead to incorrect path calculations. But even more fundamentally, the apparent elegance of the method is

misleading. The sum $3 + \frac{1}{7 + \frac{1}{4 + \frac{1}{6}}}$ may look intellectually appealing in **that** form, but its **actual** form is 3.138121..., which provides scant visual clue to its underlying structure. In this case, we can only perceive the 3 and, with a modicum of effort, the 7 (which follows because $\frac{1}{7+1} < 0.138121 \dots \leq \frac{1}{7}$): it is difficult to “see past” the 7.

By way of contrast, the **prime-tree-encoding** project on GitHub relies upon prime factorization as its workhorse and somehow encodes PTs using towers of prime numbers $a^{b^{c^d}}$ [2]. One appreciates the aesthetic appeal—as well as the Gödelian rigor—of using prime factorization as the foundation of a discrete model. However, working with enormous integers is **prohibitively computationally expensive**. Cappello employs prime factorization in a rather more rigid fashion to construct a purported bijection from the naturals onto the **unordered trees** [4]. The crux of his scheme is that (a) each prime p_i corresponds to a specific, recombinant primitive tree—mandatorily deformed *ab initio* when i is prime—and (b) each unique factorization $\prod_j p_j^{n_j}$ corresponds to a root whose children include n_j copies of primitive tree p_j . However, the system is unable to attach arbitrary copies of primitive trees at arbitrary positions below the root. The claim of bijection would be stronger if, *e.g.*, recasting $6776 = 2^3 \times 7 \times 11^2$ as $(2^3 \times 11) \times (7 \times 11)$ or $(2^2 \times 7) \times (2 \times 11^2)$ yielded two new trees, which it does not. More generally, one could adopt a graph-theoretic approach that employs prime factorization to encode the **adjacency matrix** of a PT, assigning sequential prime labels to the nodes according to a fixed scheme and subsequently representing every connection from child node a to parent node b via the factor a^b . Some savings in calculating with huge numbers could be achieved by instead representing each a^b factor as a^n , where $P = \{ p_i \}$ is the set of all primes and $p_n = b \gg n$, but the numbers are still enormous for any PT that has practical utility other than as a textbook illustration. Though optimal assignment of node labels would reduce the resultant products and thereby simplify factoring, the initial determination of an optimal labeling for a PT of realistic scale is itself an extremely computationally expensive problem.

Table 1 compares the **Wilner encoding** (WE) point by point against these variegated machinations.

Table 1. Comparison of benefits and disadvantages of various tree encoding schemes

DISADVANTAGES OF OTHER ENCODINGS	IN CONTRAST, THE WILNER ENCODING . . .
Generalized Dyck words do not establish an ordering of PTs. Neither do Prüfer sequences.	. . . imposes an intuitive, plainly seen ordering
Prüfer-type encoding is drudgingly procedural, with no overarching metaphor or pattern to be grasped.	. . . follows the “ how to draw a tree ” metaphor
Cappello’s enumeration of unordered trees cannot be bijective as claimed.	. . . maps completely and cleanly onto the space of all PTs
Decoding continued fractions requires repeated division, accruing truncation and rounding errors.	. . . fits within $\sim [3.17n]$ bits and decodes error free
Encodings based on powers of primes involve enormous, unwieldy integers that are extremely computationally expensive to factor.	. . . is a ternary proper fraction, never less than zero and always less than $\frac{2}{3}$

The foundational simplicity of the three-symbol tree-drawing paradigm has led to a formulation that is **demonstrably** more efficient, expedient, general, and powerful.

4 Conclusion

The Wilner encoding—an elegant and highly efficient mapping between the proper fractions and the complete set of plane trees (PTs)—has been introduced. The scheme incorporates a picture description language governed by a context-free grammar. The encoding is straightforward to generate and effortless to invert. It is also dramatically more practicable than any other representational scheme and will hopefully find broad acceptance and adoption.

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